

Can CLIP See Safe Streets? Comparing Human and VLM Perceptions of Walkability and Safety

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Abstract.

How *safe* does a street *look*—and can AI see it the same way humans do? We explore the use of CLIP¹, a vision–language model (VLM), to assess street-level safety in London, comparing its judgments with human annotations on street view imagery. Unlike earlier approaches like Streetscore (Naik et al., 2014), which relied on traditional ML and hand-labelled training data, we use CLIP in a zero-shot setting using prompts alone.

Understanding what makes a street feel safe is a growing concern in pedestrian navigation research, which increasingly values subjective qualities like comfort, exploration, and perceived safety over purely metric-based optimization (Yu et al., 2024; Williams et al., 2023; Fang et al., 2015; Ettema and Smajic, 2015). While zero-shot VLMs show promising results in performing visual assessment of roads (Jongwiriyannurak et al., 2024), perceived safety is a notoriously complex metric that is influenced by many factors, from lighting to neglected buildings, unsupervised dogs and presence of ‘seedy motels’ (Loukaitou-Sideris, 2006). Some features, such as trees, have shown ambiguous effects on perceived safety (Coleman et al., 2021).

To study these perceptions at scale, researchers have increasingly turned to street-level imagery, including that from Mapillary². Such imagery has been used to study urban features and assess walkability and greenery (Liu et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2024), road safety (Yu et al., 2024), and presence of CCTV cameras (Sheng et al., 2021).

We collected and manually labelled a dataset of 500 street view images, representing 100 street segments in five areas of London. Thirteen labels were assigned by three annotators, ranging from objective features (e.g., presence of *streetlight* or *traffic light*) to more subjective ones (*safe*, *green*, *busy*, *wide*).

CLIP learns image–text embeddings by mapping semantically similar images and text close together in a shared vector space. We applied zero-shot classification using CLIP, with five images per street segment and a set of five positive and five negative prompts per image. Each image was classified independently, and the final label for the street segment was determined by majority vote across the five image-level predictions—allowing us to compare how closely CLIP’s judgments align with human perception.

Example positive and negative prompts to classify street safety: ‘The area feels risky or threatening’.

Table 1 summarises CLIP’s performance across 13 urban perception labels, ranging from objective to subjective features.

Label	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 Score
Streetlight	0.75	0.85	0.79	0.81
Traffic light	0.75	0.52	0.46	0.49
Sidewalk	0.65	0.95	0.66	0.78
Crosswalk	0.84	0.47	0.60	0.53
Building	0.75	0.97	0.75	0.85
Abandoned building	0.93	0.54	0.88	0.67
CCTV	0.92	0.20	1.00	0.33
Shop	0.82	0.63	0.45	0.53
Wide street	0.68	0.63	0.63	0.63
Busy street	0.74	0.69	0.62	0.65
Road condition	0.89	0.95	0.94	0.94
Green	0.59	0.81	0.61	0.70
Safe	0.90	0.95	0.93	0.94

Table 1. Classification results on 100 street segments (5 images per each street segment) across labels using CLIP.

Overall, CLIP proved to be a capable zero-shot classifier for street view imagery, which is consistent with the find-

¹<https://github.com/openai/CLIP>

²<https://www.mapillary.com/>

Figure 1. Where CLIP and humans disagree on safety. Top row: safe according to CLIP, unsafe according to a human labeller. Bottom row: unsafe according to CLIP, but safe according to a human labeller.

ings from Liu et al. (2023). The low F1 score for CCTV can be explained by severe dataset imbalance (only 2 positives). We find that CLIP’s perception of street safety often aligns with human judgment, achieving an F1 score of 0.94 for the ‘safe’ label. This suggests that zero-shot VLMs may already hold usable priors about urban safety, although Figure 1 demonstrates the complexity of the problem.

Our results motivate a larger-scale study to identify which urban features most influence human and AI perceptions of safety, and where they diverge. This could inform both walkability analysis and the development of human-aligned urban AI systems.

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